

**Political cycles of forest rents
in developing countries**

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Abstract

In this article, we question the presence of electoral cycles in forest rents in developing countries. The presence of rents can be an additional motivation to stay in power, they can be used to finance elections without running a deficit or increasing taxes. Forests' point resource characteristics make them more subject to political cycles. Moreover, we focus on developing countries because of the quality of their institutions. The study covers eighty-three (83) developing countries from 1990 to 2018, using the method of ordinary least squares corrected for the possible Nickell's bias. The results show that only competitive elections ensure the presence of cycles within forest rents. This presence of cycles in the event of competitive elections is robust to using different robustness tests. These cycles appear only in the event of representation of the candidate in power at the elections, in low-corrupted and high-human-freedom countries.

Keywords: Political cycles, Forest rents, Panel data, Developing countries.

JEL codes: C23, D72, E62, O13, O50, Q3

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1 Introduction

The quality of institutions is a central element in the development of a country. However, in a large part of the developing countries, it is lacking. The same goes for democracy, which can still be a luxury for most developing countries because of the difficulty of implementing and maintaining it in these countries. This situation can be explained by the absence of a democratic tradition and other structural factors such as the mobilization of the masses based on identity (manipulation of these masses on ethnic bases) [Rodrik \(2016\)](#). As a result, electoral manipulation can be tempting, so recurrent in these countries.

Incumbents are ready to do anything to stay in power in developing countries that are also often endowed with natural resources. The resources, and the forest resources in particular, constitute an essential source of financing for the economies of these countries. For example, [Huang *et al.* \(2020\)](#) shows that forest rents significantly contributed to the growth of developing countries in Asia between 1996 and 2016. In short, several developing countries are characterized by poor democratic experience, institutional weakness, and natural resource richness.

These forest rents can be diverted from their primary role of financing development to financing re-elections. Indeed, the manipulation of elections is quite commonplace in developing countries. Politicians use natural resource rents to stay in power. Economic literature reports on these political manipulations, and this is what we find in the works of [Nordhaus \(1975\)](#), [Rogoff et Sibert \(1988\)](#), and [Shi et Svensson \(2006\)](#). The manipulations are due to the voters' solid preferences for physical well-being and high economic performance, as highlighted by [Paldam \(2004\)](#) and [Franzese Jr \(2002\)](#).

Moreover, this motivation to remain in power is more significant in the presence of natural resources. The presence of rents alters the conditions of the game, since the incumbent has an extra string to his bow to fund spending to appease voters. Indeed, although voters have strong preferences for physical well-being and high economic performance, they can punish the candidate in the presence of a huge deficit or the event

of a tax increase [Huntington \(1993\)](#) notes. Thus, rents are a means for the incumbent to finance his re-election. They are a way to finance re-election without incurring the wrath of voters who do not see them as lost revenue, as in the case of taxes used for re-election purposes. In this logic, [McGuirk \(2013\)](#) and [Bornhorst *et al.* \(2009\)](#) point out that rents represent a loosening of the fiscal constraint on the incumbent.

In addition to increasing the risk of the appearance of political cycles, the abundance of rents, particularly from forests, has other repercussions on the countries that have them. Studies have shown the adverse effects of the abundance of natural resources. The starting point of this work was the paper of [Auty *et al.* \(1998\)](#) and that of [Sachs *et al.* Warner \(1995\)](#), which show that countries rich in natural resources have slower growth than those less endowed. This adverse effect has subsequently been shown to depend on the quality of institutions, as we can see in [Mehlum *et al.* \(2006\)](#) and [Sala-i Martin *et al.* Subramanian \(2013\)](#). Because institutional quality is low in most developing countries, resources can lead to adverse effects. Among these effects is the lack of stable political systems. The two leading explanations are that these resources create the conditions for armed conflict ([Collier *et al.* Hoeffler \(2002\)](#)). This was the case in Liberia and is still the case in Congo. The second explanation is that these resources reduce the quality of institutions, especially fiscal institutions, which no longer make an effort to collect taxes. Moreover, again, candidates will do anything to control this rent([Jensen *et al.* Wantchekon \(2004\)](#)).

These different theories have significant implications for developing countries. Indeed, weak institutions characterize these countries. The absence of real checks and balances and long-term economic reforms characterizes the political landscape. Thus, the various theories of fiscal-political cycles assume the quality of institutions and the presence of free and competitive elections. These assumptions are problematic because of the institutional weakness and non-competitiveness of elections in developing countries.

The present work fills a gap in the literature on electoral cycles in natural resource

rents in developing countries. Because the models developed to explain the presence of political-fiscal cycles implicitly assume the presence of regular and competitive elections [Nordhaus \(1975\)](#), [Rogoff et Sibert \(1988\)](#) and [Shi et Svensson \(2006\)](#). For example, [Block \(2001\)](#) shows in his paper that the political cycles are higher at the level of competitive elections in developing countries. However, even in the presence of uncompetitive or non-competitive elections, such as can be observed in developing countries, we can observe political cycles at the level of rents. Indeed, the need to finance additional expenditures, acquire an electoral base, or ensure the support of its partners requires the mobilization of resources, which is facilitated by the presence of rents in natural resources. The candidate could use the rents, and in this case, forest rents, to finance his re-election, which is no longer guaranteed in advance given the high level of electoral competition, or to ensure the loyalty of its employees even if the elections are not competitive. Also, the literature places very little emphasis on forest resources. Authors like [Klomp et de Haan \(2016\)](#) briefly mention this when analyzing the heterogeneity of their results and find no cycles in forest rents. Furthermore, it is also in this logic that our paper makes its contribution to literature. The interest of a study centered on forest rents lies in the fact that this directly impacts deforestation. So political cycles at the level of rents can therefore have environmental implications. Forest rents are easily manipulated due to the non-necessity of prospecting before exploitation. Thus, the government can more easily grant logging permits on the eve of the elections. This paper aims to shed light on these possible cycles through a macroeconomic study of developing countries. The literature shows us, on the one hand, that rents, in general, are positively linked to the duration of the power of presidents because of the desire to control these rents. This same literature shows the use of annuities for re-election purposes. Thus, in our study, forest rents should increase during the election period, especially during competitive elections. Through this study, we perform a wide range of robustness and especially heterogeneity tests to understand the cycles in these countries better.

In order to do so, we estimate a dynamic panel model on developing countries using the method of least squares corrected for the bias of [Nickell \(1981\)](#). The fact that we focus on these specific countries limits our options regarding the estimation methods that could be used. We cannot use the fixed effects estimator because of the [Nickell \(1981\)](#) bias. A second alternative is the use of GMM estimators. However, given the large number of conditions to be fulfilled in this method, it is used in robustness. It is in this logic that we turned to the method of least squares corrected for the bias of [Nickell \(1981\)](#). This method was initiated by [Bruno \(2005\)](#), allowing for estimating the dynamic panels. It is based on an approximation of the Nickell bias to remove this bias from the fixed effects estimation. The originality of the implemented method is also linked to the fact that it is appropriate for non-cylindrical panels. Before the work of [Bruno \(2005\)](#), which extended the bias approximation to non-cylindrical panels, it was impossible to apply this methodology to the latter. Monte Carlo experiments have shown that this estimator outperforms estimators based on the generalized method of moments, as already pointed out by [Judson et Owen \(1999\)](#).

Our results suggest that, in general, we do not have political cycles in developing countries at the level of forest rents, but these cycles appear for competitive elections. These results align with the literature that assumes the presence of competitive elections leads to the presence of political cycles. These results are robust to our various robustness tests. Our results have also shown that, as expected from the literature, they only appear if the candidate in power is represented in the elections in low-corrupted countries and countries with high human freedom.

The rest of the paper is presented as follows: in section [2](#), we review the literature relevant to our work. First, the one dealing with political-budgetary cycles, then the one dealing with natural resource rents and, more specifically, rent-seeking behavior for re-election purposes. Section [2.3](#) will be dedicated to presenting our hypotheses. Section [3](#) presents the data we used to carry out our study, descriptive statistics, and stylized facts. The above methodology will be more fully described in section [4](#) of our work. This

section contains the model to be estimated and our chosen estimation methodology. Our results will then be presented in section 5, the robustness and heterogeneity of which will be presented in section 6 and 7 section, respectively.

2 Political cycles and forest rents: An overview of the literature

This work aims to study political cycles within forest rents in developing countries. Therefore, we relate the literature on political-budgetary cycles and the literature on the effect of natural resources, particularly forest resources, on the political sphere. Thus, we will first study literature that deals with political-budgetary cycles. The second literature that will be studied deals with natural resources, specifically forest resources.

2.1 Political and budgetary cycles in developing countries

A political budget cycle is a cycle in specific government budget components induced by electoral cycles. Put another way, this term refers to an increase in public spending or deficit or a decrease in taxation in an election year, the objective of which is to favor the incumbent's re-election. There are two explanations for pre-election cycles, which are often contradictory. The first explanation is that the incumbent may change government spending, the deficit, or taxation to please voters who prefer low levels of taxation or high levels of government spending. However, this explanation is difficult to reconcile with voter rationality. Indeed, a rational voter would understand the manipulations of the outgoing candidate and will not be deceived in this case. The second explanation is that voters prefer good economic conditions (such as low unemployment or economic growth) and would therefore be more likely to vote for the incumbent who would provide them with that.

Regarding the theoretical literature on the subject, [Nordhaus \(1975\)](#) and [MacRae \(1977\)](#) are the first articles to address the issue of political-budgetary cycles specifically.

They model the occurrence of political-fiscal cycles. What can be retained from these first models is that during an election period, the incumbent will create inflation to take advantage of the relative advantage offered by the Philips curve in the short term¹ compared with the long term. However, these adaptive expectations models had to be revisited to consider rational expectations. Agents who understand the government's will are not fooled because of rational expectations. Following these articles and pioneering models, [Rogoff et Sibert \(1988\)](#) present a model where the government tries to send signals of its competence to the population. The authors argue that the electoral cycles of some macroeconomic variables are due to a temporal informational asymmetry. A voter cannot observe the candidate's competence. The main elements of these models can be found in the basic model of [Rogoff \(1990\)](#). The major criticism to the above models is that we have to deal with results models; that is, political power can finely manipulate macroeconomic aggregates. However, it is difficult for even a candidate for power to manipulate these aggregates directly. Recent literature, therefore, emphasizes cycles involving economic policy instruments such as public expenditure. [Shi et Svensson \(2006\)](#) develop a model where they use a moral hazard model to explain political cycles. In this model, the magnitude of a budgetary election cycle depends on the politician's motivation to stay in power and the share of voters unaware of the politician's manipulative objectives.

As already noted above, the authors try to explain that voters allow themselves to be convinced by the last-minute manipulations of the politician who wants to remain in power through informational asymmetry. This informational asymmetry may correspond to the age of democracy, in which case voters do not have the necessary hindsight to understand the maneuvers of the politician in power or to access information. The experience of the electorate plays an essential role in its capacity to understand the manipulations, as underlined by [Brender et Drazen \(2005\)](#). This informational asym-

¹The Phillips curve works on the principle of monetary illusion or nominal illusions. Employers reason in terms of real wages, while employees reason in nominal terms. Thus, inflation in the short run reduces unemployment, since employers will hire if inflation is higher than nominal wage growth. Also, this inflation, by increasing nominal wages, inflation increases consumption.

metry may also correspond to access to information. Indeed, the lack or non-access of the population to information on the management of natural resources or the candidate's motivations in power means that the leader can easily take advantage of it to find additional funds to ensure his re-election. This is what the authors of [Brender \(2003\)](#) and [Shi et Svensson \(2006\)](#) also tell us. They show that the impossibility on the part of the voters to distinguish the manipulations made for re-election increases the manipulations made by the incumbent.

The first article to empirically test the theory of budgetary-political cycles is [Tufte \(1978\)](#), which was a study of the specific case of the United States of America. However, a panoply of articles followed this first work. One of the most recent papers in this field concerning African countries is that of [Iddrisu et Bokpin \(2018\)](#). A very recent paper by [Boly et al. \(2023\)](#) shows us the presence of political cycles in CO2 emissions, demonstrating the presence of manipulation on the part of the incumbent candidate for re-election purposes. This last paper is of particular interest to us because, like us, it shows that elections can have an impact on the environment.

In the literature, some articles highlight cycles in developing countries. This is what we can read in [Block et al. \(2003\)](#)'s paper and that of [Mosley et Chiripanhura \(2016\)](#). However, applying the theory of political-fiscal cycles to developing countries raises questions. Indeed, the usual theories are based on a certain institutional quality that guarantees free and competitive elections. We need to break down these assumptions to test these theories in developing countries. By questioning this given level of institutions, we will directly impact the model's predictions, as authors such as [Schultz \(1995\)](#) and [Block \(2002\)](#) point out. In the case of non-competitive elections, the incumbent may not need to create distortion. Indeed, his risk of losing the election is almost zero. Thus, considering this context of developing countries, we expect cycles of low amplitude in general.

Several components of the state budget are subject to political-budgetary cycles. Whether on the expenditure or revenue side, the incumbent does not hesitate to use

each budgetary and tax policy component to get re-elected. Forest rents constitute a means for the candidate for power to finance his re-election, and the literature has looked into the question. The literature highlights the advantage that natural resource rents confer on the candidate for [Smith \(2004\)](#), [Goldberg *et al.* \(2008\)](#), and [Aaskoven \(2020\)](#). Nevertheless, before going further on the relationship between forest rents and the political sphere, we will present in the next section the question of rents in forest resources in developing countries before showing their interaction with the political sphere.

2.2 Forest rents and their interaction with the political sphere

The abundance of natural resources should be a blessing for the countries that possess them. However, in many cases, the abundance of natural resources, especially their exploitation, has harmed countries. This contradictory effect of the abundance of natural resources can be explained by Sachs' theory of the curse of natural resources [Sachs et Warner \(2001\)](#). According to authors including [Corden et Neary \(1982\)](#), the discovery of resources leads to a fall in income due to a rise in the real exchange rate. [Collier \(2010\)](#) shows an interaction between the endowment of natural resources and the quality of institutions. When asked why natural resource endowments worsen the political situation in developing countries, one of the author's arguments is the lack of accountability of leaders to the population, in other words, the deterioration of the quality of institutions. Indeed, the abundance of natural resources creates a decline in institutional quality, which in turn creates a decline in economic growth. [Leite et Weidmann \(1999\)](#) was among the first papers to show the decline in institutional quality due to natural resources. Other papers like [Sala-i Martin et Subramanian \(2013\)](#) and [Isham *et al.* \(2005\)](#) show that natural resources negatively impact economic activity when one fails to set up institutions. In the case of forest resources, it should be noted that it is a point resource. Unlike diffuse resources, point resources are spatially concentrated and can easily be controlled [Bulte *et al.* \(2005\)](#). Hence, point resources are

those that have a negative impact on institutions. These are, for example, oil resources, minerals, and plantations. The political sphere could be affected by the harmful effects of the abundance of natural resources and forest resources, which are a point resource.

Prima facie, significant revenues from natural resources have two effects on the incentives of political actors. First, the incumbent will have a greater incentive to stay in power and use all means to stay there. This could lead to political-fiscal cycles. Second, other candidates will be more motivated to run for office, thus increasing electoral competition. Moreover, the fact that forests are easily exploitable, unlike minerals, makes their rents more easily manipulated.

In practical terms, large amounts of forest resources in a country affect the politician's behavior: The politician will have more motivation to stay in power. Then the electoral competition will be more significant, and the incumbent will do whatever it takes to stay in power. Leaders may be willing to use tactics such as repression or corruption to stay in power. Following this logic, leaders could increase rents before elections to curry favor with the ruling class through a symbolic system of exchange [Médard \(1991\)](#). Indeed, the incumbent must have as much support as possible to safeguard power. This is why he distributes forest rents to the country's elite. A rentier state sees its obligations of transparency and accountability to the population diminished since rents sometimes replace the existing tax system. Thus, rents lead, in the long run, to a situation where the population demands a minor change in a political regime ([Beblawi et Luciani \(2015\)](#)).

[Aaskoven \(2020\)](#) shows that the use of natural resource rents can be obtained in two ways: directly, increasing revenues from the mining industry and from national mining companies. However, in the case of African countries, most mining companies are private, and therefore the state will go through taxation to increase its revenues from natural resources. Another more specific study [Uberti et al. \(2019\)](#) shows us that governments can also go through unofficial channels to take advantage of the manna offered by natural resource rents to finance the incumbent's re-election. The candidate

can increase production by increasing operating licenses instead of increasing taxation in the mining sector during an election period. According to the literature, the punctual or diffuse nature of the natural resource can impact its interaction with the political sphere. With regard to forest resources, it should be noted that unlike other resources, which require several studies and several years before their exploitation, they are more easily exploitable. Also, the forest often belongs to the states. Such a situation favors policies aimed at increasing the rent before the elections.

From all the above, we see that few studies focus on forest rents. Next, most of the articles conduct studies on political cycles from countries with a high level of electoral competition, thus excluding a good number of developing countries. We propose in this study to investigate the presence of political cycles at the level of forest rents in developing countries by taking into account the level of competitiveness of elections.

2.3 Our Assumptions

From the preceding, we attempt in this paper to highlight the presence of political cycles at the level of forest rents in developing countries. The literature mainly focuses on successful democracies, leaving by example aside many developing countries, particularly those in sub-Saharan Africa. Then the studies very often focus on specific resources such as oil. We propose to study the presence of political cycles at the level of forest resources in developing countries. Therefore, in this paper, we will test a set of hypotheses that will allow us to shed light on the cycles in natural resource rents.

1. Political cycles in natural resource rents depend on the level of election competition. Overall, at the level of developing countries, we do not expect to detect electoral cycles in forest rents. Weak institutions and uncompetitive elections provide little incentive for incumbents to generate distortions to stay in power. However, a higher level of electoral competition may force the incumbent to use these rents to ensure he remains in power.

2. Different resources are not impacted similarly by upcoming elections. The same

literature shows the difference between the intensive capital resources and those less intensive. Intensive capital resources require more investment for their extraction, and therefore the extraction decision of these resources depends less on the political sphere and more than one choice of investment. Thus, this is another reason to believe that we will see political cycles in forest rents. In addition and above all, forest resources are point resources. This increases the probability of having political cycles.

3 Data and Descriptive Statistics

In this section, we first present our variables and their sources in subsection 3.1, and then present descriptive statistics for our variables in subsection 3.2.

3.1 Definition of variables

Our sample comprises eighty-three (83) developing countries. The list of countries included in the analysis is in the Appendix, in table 6. We looked for electoral cycles in these countries from 1990 to 2018. This time horizon was dictated by data availability.

The measurement of forest rents: `Forest_rent`

The measure we will use here is the one introduced by [Collier et Hoeffler \(2009\)](#) that considers the fluctuation of world prices and extraction costs. The World Bank published the data for this new measure of rents [Lange et al. \(2018\)](#). This dependent variable of natural resources has advantages, such as disaggregating it into different types of resources. This global database gives us the rents for different resources, and we will focus on the forest rents in accordance with our subject. This variable does not directly measure the share of rents going to the state accounts, but is a good approximation. [Klomp et de Haan \(2016\)](#) showed a significant and strong correlation between the level of rents and state income from rents.

The variable of interest: Elect

Our variable of interest is the election period. In the previous literature dealing with issues of fiscal-political cycles, the variable used to capture the election period is a dummy variable taking the value of 1 in election years and 0 in other years. However, this measure of election years can be improved. [Franzese \(2000\)](#) did it by proposing an alternative measure to this discrete measure. The proposed measure is a measure whose sum gives one, and this unit is split between the year of the election and the year before the election. Practically, [Franzese \(2000\)](#) creates the variable $elect_t$ for the election in year t , which is equal to $(M/12) + (d/D)/12$ the year of the election with M the number of full months before the election, d the number of whole days in the month before the election and finally D the number of whole days in the year. In the year before the election, this variable is equal to $1 - ((M/12) + (d/D)/12)$. The simplified version of this variable was used in [Klomp et de Haan \(2016\)](#). In the latter case, both authors defined their variable as $M/12$ in the election year and $(12 - M)/12$ in the year before the election. This variable allows for capturing the election period more accurately because it captures the electoral period more precisely. Indeed, let us imagine that the election was on February 1, 2000. The standard measure would have taken discrete would have taken the whole year 2000 as the election year, while the campaign mainly took place in 1999. This *Elect* variable includes the elections that took place at the scheduled times and those that were delayed. Referring to the literature, we expect to see either a positive and significant sign or non-significance for this variable, but definitely not negative and significant.

Considering the competition level: Elect_Con

In our study, we will consider the level of competition in the elections. As already mentioned above, some papers, as [Schultz \(1995\)](#); [Block \(2002\)](#), questioned the assumptions made by the models explaining the political budgetary cycles. And as our study concerns developing countries, which are not all democratic, it is necessary to take account of the level of elections' competitiveness. To do this, our electoral variable

will be weighted by an index giving the level of political constraint. Our political constraint variable comes from the database developed by [Henisz \(2005\)](#). The weighting makes it possible to retain the greatest number of elections, which makes it possible to have more observations with a non-zero election period. Second, weighting allows us to retain the greatest variability within our variable, whereas excluding non-competitive elections would cause us to lose this variability. Finally, it avoids the exclusion of non-competitive elections. The exclusion of non-competitive elections must be done based on a threshold, and this threshold would be done on an arbitrary basis, which we avoid using the weighting method.

The POLCON database was developed by [Henisz \(2005\)](#) with the aim of taking into account the feasibility of policy change on the part of the government. In other words, how the change in the point of view of one of the actors affects the country's politics. However, this initial measure was improved to consider the heterogeneity within the main political parties. In his study, the author shows that homogeneity within the opposition party, a united opposition party, was a sign of great political constraint. This variable can therefore be used as a proxy for competition and the quality of elections. Indeed, this variable measures the existing counter-power. And strong checks and balances means that the president in power must prove himself to stay in power and can therefore be ejected at the end of his term, which makes elections more competitive. Taking into account the level of election competition, we expect to have a positive and significant sign for the *Elect_Con* variable.

Control variables

We first include institutional variables such as the level of corruption (Corruption) and level of democracy (Democ) of the country have been added as control variables. The institutional factor is essential in determining a given country's rent level. Above all, the literature on the effects of natural resource rents shows us that one of the key determinants is the institutional factor [Mehlum et al. \(2006\)](#). It is, therefore, necessary

to include this factor in our analyses.

Then comes the gross domestic product (GDP) per capita level to consider the development level. The empirical literature underlines the role of economic development on the occurrence or magnitude of political-fiscal cycles. Already, the literature points out that such cycles are more likely to occur in the least developed countries. Several factors can explain this result. According to [Shi et Svensson \(2006\)](#), this is mainly due to differences in the institutional environment, while [Brender et Drazen \(2005\)](#) points to the weak democratic experience of low-income countries.

Our third variable is the rate of depletion of natural resources (Depl). This variable has been used in the literature as a proxy for the level of natural resource rents globally. We use this variable instead of the total rent variable because it is mechanically linked to the level of forest resource rents, which is only one component. This variable of the rate of depletion of natural resources has the role of taking into account the mining activity of the country. It shows the pressure on forest rents since the more other natural resources are depleted, the more countries will be tempted to turn to forest resources. Although calculated on the basis of unit rents, the depletion rate only takes into account the excess of rents over natural growth. It therefore takes into account the endowment of natural resources, which reflects a country's wealth in natural resources.

The last variable to be added is the urbanization rate (UrbanPop) to take into account the part of the population that is subject to manipulations to the cycles. Indeed, in developing countries, the urban population is the most educated and able to understand the political programs of the various candidates. The urban population, therefore, impacts the occurrence of political cycles because, in developing countries, a large proportion of the urban population is the best-informed and has their finger on the political pulse. Rural populations are usually disconnected from the rest of the country and are poorly served by the public network.

3.2 Descriptive Statistics

This section on descriptive statistics describes the variables over our entire study period. We are working on 83 developing countries over the period 1990-2018.

Already, the graph 1 shows the level of forest rents for the first year of our study period. It shows that most of the countries in our sample are countries with forest rents. Central African countries are highly dependent on forest rents, which is only logical given their forest resources level. The countries of Latin America, on the other hand, although rich in forest resources, are not heavily dependent on these rents.

Figure 1: Forest Rents in 1990 for countries in our sample
Sources: World Development Indicators

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	N	Mean	SD	SE	Min	Max	Measurement unity
Forest_rent	2368	3.0044	4.9857	0.1025	0.0000	36.0683	% of GDP
GDPperCap	2345	5045.0717	8613.2618	177.8673	164.3366	16648.7700	Constant Dollar
Democ	2377	3.9348	9.3384	0.1915	0	10	Index (0 to 10)
UrbanPop	2384	51.6228	21.7195	0.4448	11.0760	95.3340	% of Population
Corruption	2338	2.4300	0.9931	0.0205	0	6	Index (0 to 6)
Depl	2287	5.1173	6.8708	0.1437	0.0000	68.5665	% of GNI
Polcon	2218	0.2723	0.2080	0.0044	0.000	0.7256	Index (0 to 1)
Elect	2384	0.1293	0.2840	0.0058	0.000	1.0000	.

After studying the graph 1, we review the main descriptive statistics of our variables,

summarized in the table 1. Our dependent variable, the level of forest rents, has a mean of 3% of GDP. This means that, on average, in our sample, the countries are endowed with forest resources whereby generating forest rents as shown in graph 1. However, this level of forest rent is highly variable since the standard deviation is significant (4.985), larger than the average (3.004). Looking at the GDP per capita variable, we notice that our sample is quite heterogeneous and includes countries that are both rich and those with modest incomes. Indeed, here again, the standard deviation is far above the average. The same observation holds for the level of democracy. Our sample of 83 countries contains democratic as well as non-democratic countries, as we can see by looking at the *Democ* variable.

Figure 2: Average rents during electoral and non-electoral periods
Sources: Author calculation, WDI rent database and NELDA database

According to our assumptions, we should observe an increase in forest rents during the election period. In practice, this translates into higher average levels of forest rents during the election period. We see this in the graph 2. Indeed, although the difference is slight, we see that the level of rents during the election period is higher.

The second key element of our study is to consider the level of competitiveness of the elections. For this purpose, we use the political constraint variable (*POLCON*). Graph 3 shows a negative relationship between the level of political constraint and the level of rents, since the slope of the regression line is negative. So, a political constraint is associated with greater institutional quality and lower rent dependence.

Figure 3: Relationship between Forest rents and Political constraint
 Sources: Author calculation, WDI rent database and POLCON database

A final point in favor of our hypotheses is the positive relationship between the level of forest rents and the length of time politicians have been in power, shown by graph 5. This positive relationship between natural resource rents and length of time in power was highlighted by [Désiré Omgba \(2007\)](#).

These different statistics give us a first glimpse of the relationships between the variables. However, we must consider a whole set of other interactions to effectively isolate the relationship we want to study. This is what we will do through our econometric approach.

4 Econometric framework

We rely on a dynamic specification, which is theoretically interesting because it assumes a steady state value of the forest rent, towards which one country convergences conditionally on the Election variable and other conditioning factors. Furthermore, this is due to the inertia effect of resource rents. It makes, however, the estimates sensitive to the Nickell' bias ([Nickell \(1981\)](#)). This will lead us to a second part to discuss the choice of the estimator then.

4.1 Econometric model

Regarding the econometric specification, we will use two approaches. The first approach will allow us to search for cycles in forest rents in elections, and the second will allow us to do so by taking into account the level of competitiveness of elections. We will therefore have the following two equations:

$$Forest_rent_{it} = \omega_i + \delta_t + \theta Forest_rent_{it-1} + \phi Elect_{it} + \psi Z_{it} + v_{it} \quad (1)$$

$$Forest_rent_{it} = \omega_i + \delta_t + \theta Forest_rent_{it-1} + \phi Elect_{it} + \rho Polcon_{it} + \beta Elect_Con_{it} + \psi Z_{it} + v_{it} \quad (2)$$

In the two equations, the subscripts i and t indicate the country and year involved. $Forest_rent_{it}$ represents the forest rents variable as a percentage of GDP. The variable $Forest_rent_{it-1}$ denotes the lagged value of the dependent variable. We will focus here on why we included this lagged variable. The reason is quite simple; a country does not become rentier overnight. Thus, a country with rents in an election year will likely have had rents the year before.

The variable ω_i is the variable that controls for the unobservable characteristics of the different countries in our sample; these are the country-fixed effects. The variable δ_t captures the time-fixed effects, that is, the unobservable characteristics of each year. The variable $Elect_{it}$ refers to our variable indicating the pre-election period. Z_{it} refers to our model's set of control variables. These explanatory variables are supposed to partly explain the rents received by the different countries, and we base ourselves on the literature for the choice of these variables. In equation 2 only, the variable $Polcon_{it}$ refers to our electoral competition variable, and finally, the variable $Elect_Con_{it}$ is the interaction between our electoral variable $Elect_{it}$ and the variable $Polcon_{it}$.

4.2 The estimation method

The lagged variable in our specification makes the econometric techniques commonly used in the case of panel data inefficient. The Fixed Effects (FE) method is unsuitable for our specification because it would negatively correlate the error term and the lagged endogenous variable. This negative correlation of the fixed effects estimator is known as the Nickell's bias ([Nickell \(1981\)](#)).

We are moving towards another method, it consists of correcting the bias generated using ordinary least squares. The idea behind this method is to approximate the bias generated by the estimation with the inappropriate estimators to remove this bias from the estimation of the parameters. This method is based on the work of [Nickell \(1981\)](#). Indeed, in addition to highlighting the inadequacy of Ordinary Least Squares due to the bias, [Nickell \(1981\)](#) tried to approximate this bias. However, the different approximations were not operational. We had to wait for more recent works to consider the bias in estimating the parameters. Monte Carlo simulations were performed to obtain the properties of the bias-corrected ordinary least squares estimator. These simulations showed that bias-corrected OLS outperforms the instrumental variable and GMM methods in terms of bias. Work such as [Bun et Kiviet \(2003\)](#) has successfully approximated up to 90% of the bias. We turned to the version of this estimator developed for unbalanced panels. This is the version developed by [Bruno \(2005\)](#), which is adapted to unbalanced panels. It prevents us from losing data if we limit ourselves to non-cylindrical panels. This methodology is becoming increasingly used in the literature ([Trabelsi \(2016\)](#); [Gootjes *et al.* \(2021\)](#); [Debrun *et al.* \(2008\)](#)), making it possible to perform certain types of studies on groups of countries, which was not possible with the GMM estimators.

The standard solution usually used is the Generalized Moment Method (GMM). It is a method adapted to dynamic panel studies by controlling for the endogeneity of the variables that cause us problems while controlling for country and time-fixed effects. However, this method is challenging to implement because of the many conditions to be

respected for valid results. Conditions which are described in detail by [Roodman \(2009\)](#). Indeed, in order to validate the results following the use of the Generalized Method of Moments, the coefficient of the lagged dependent variable must be significant and less than 1. Then, due to the presence of the lagged variable, we expect the presence of an autoregressive process of order 1 (AR(1)). However, there is no reason for there to be an autoregressive process of order 2 (AR(2)). And finally, the instrumental variables must be valid and this is verified through the sargan test or that

In practice, bias-corrected ordinary least squares are obtained in two steps. The first step is to estimate the bias, and the second is to extract the bias from the ordinary least squares estimate. First, for bias estimation, three methods are available. These methods are described by [Bruno \(2005\)](#). The different bias approximations are: $B_1 = c_1(T^{-1})$, $B_2 = B_1 + c_2(N^1T^{-2})$, $B_3 = B_2 + c_3(N^1T^{-2})$ with N the number of study units and $T = (1/N)\sum_1^N T_i$ presents the average panel size of the group. Then, three estimators can be implemented to estimate this bias, depending on the type of bias chosen for the correction. It can be estimated either using the [Anderson et Hsiao \(1981\)](#) estimator or the difference estimator of [Arellano et Bond \(1991\)](#), or the system estimator of [Blundell et Bond \(1998\)](#). It should be noted here that the Nickell bias-corrected least squares method is not a GMM estimator but uses GMM estimators to estimate Nickell's bias. Once the bias has been estimated, the equation $MCOC_i = MCO - B_i$, $i = 1, 2$ or 3 can now be solved. The error term is obtained by a bootstrap method.

We have chosen the most rigorous definition of bias for our case, that is to say, the third definition. Furthermore, for our main regressions, we chose to estimate it using the Blundell-Bond estimator. However, our main results are reproduced by following the other two estimators, Arellano-Bond and Anderson-Hsiao. Moreover, we chose 100 bootstraps to calculate the error term.

Table 2: Main Results

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
	OLS	LSDVC	OLS	LSDVC	OLS	LSDVC	OLS	LSDVC
L.Forest_rent	0.6831*** (0.0160)	0.7820*** (0.0157)	0.6531*** (0.0164)	0.7596*** (0.0163)	0.6571*** (0.0167)	0.7546*** (0.0191)	0.6213*** (0.0169)	0.7266*** (0.0210)
Elect	-0.1294 (0.1029)	-0.1304 (0.1273)	-0.3932** (0.1659)	-0.4217** (0.1711)	-0.1525 (0.1057)	-0.1529 (0.1093)	-0.4508*** (0.1721)	-0.4826*** (0.1707)
Elect_Con			0.8616* (0.4672)	0.9465** (0.4534)			0.9409** (0.4784)	1.0350** (0.5005)
Polcon			-0.8726*** (0.2125)	-0.9307*** (0.2626)			-1.0470*** (0.2280)	-1.1070*** (0.2633)
Corruption					-0.1047** (0.0483)	-0.1176** (0.0535)	-0.1412*** (0.0491)	-0.1560*** (0.0559)
GDPperCap					0.0001** (0.0000)	0.0001** (0.0000)	0.0000 (0.0000)	0.0000 (0.0000)
Depl					0.0485*** (0.0086)	0.0450*** (0.0109)	0.0625*** (0.0089)	0.0570*** (0.0109)
UrbanPop					0.0063 (0.0114)	0.0118 (0.0156)	0.0063 (0.0125)	0.0146 (0.0177)
Democ					-0.0058 (0.0040)	-0.0053 (0.0047)	-0.0016 (0.0042)	-0.0011 (0.0044)
<i>N</i>	2285	2298	2119	2119	2180	2180	2010	2010
Country FE	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Year FE	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
R ²	0.93		0.93		0.94		0.94	
Countries	83	83	83	83	87	87	83	83

Notes: N=2010, t statistics in parentheses; * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

We have opted to present the OLS regressions in order to present the R² of the LSDVC regressions, since technically they are the same regressions, only with the added correction of Nickell's bias. The command does not provide an R² for LSDVC regressions.

5 Results and discussion

Our main results in table 2 consist of three main parts. The first two columns of the table show us a univariate regression, considering our electoral variable (Elect) as the only explanatory variable, taking care to control by the fixed effects. The coefficient in front of the elect variable is not significant. So these two columns show us that elections generally do not give rise to increases in forest rents. The two following columns (columns 3 and 4) present a more enriched specification than the previous ones since we consider here the level of competitiveness of the elections, as described above. These columns contain three explanatory variables. They are already showing us results that meet our expectations. The coefficient in front of the interactive variable is positive and significant. Competitive elections give rise to the manipulation of forest rents for re-election purposes. Columns 5 and 6 of the same table give us the same result as in columns 1 and 2. Thus, even taking care to control by key variables, elections in general still do not give rise to political cycles at the level of forest rents. The last two columns are the most complete model of our work. They allow us to check the robustness of our results shown in columns 3 and 4 by controlling for factors that can influence the level of forest rents in a country.

In the presence of competitive elections, there is an increase in forest resource rents in our sample countries. Our main result obtained and presented in column 8 of the table allows us to say that an increase of one unit in the level of competitiveness of the elections leads to an increase in forest rents of about 1.04% of GDP. However, to have a clearer idea of what this increase represents, we must compare it to the average level (3.00) and the standard deviation (4.99) of forest rents. Thus, this increase corresponds to 34.61% of the mean and 20.84% of the standard deviation of forest rents. When we continue with this logic of comparison with the average, the increase in the level of rents is equal to 34.61% for a country whose level of rents is 2.982478. These results, therefore, show that forests, which are point resources, are subject to political cycles, following the literature decomposing natural resources into two groups: point and not

point resources.

Apart from our weighted electoral variable of the level of election competitiveness, we have other variables at the level of our final model (the last two columns), which give us interesting results. The political constraint is linked to lower forest rents. This result can be understood since this constraint reduces the risks of manipulating the exploitation rights granted to companies. The surprising result is the negative relationship between corruption and forest rents. Instead, one would expect a positive relationship between these two variables. This result refers to the ambiguity of the relationship between natural resource rents and corruption. High levels of corruption are not necessarily synonymous with high annuities, as these may not be declared in some instances. Furthermore, all the more so since, in our case, we already control by an institutional quality variable, namely the level of political constraint.

6 Robustness analysis

In this section, we present the robustness of our result when we consider the competitiveness of elections, and the results are presented in Tables 3 and 4. In the first part, we use the Anderson-Hsiao and Arellano-Bond estimators to estimate bias instead of the Blundell-Bond estimator, followed by other, less stringent bias corrections. Next, we use an alternative estimator: the GMM method. Then, in a third section, we see the magnitude of our results for resource-dependent countries. Finally, we use additional control variables and placebo tests to confirm the robustness of our results.

6.1 Use of alternative bias correction.

The command developed by the authors of our model allows us to use several estimators to estimate Nickell's bias for the correction of the Ordinary Least Square estimator. In our primary model, we use the Blundell-Bond estimator. For robustness, we use the other estimators available in the command, namely the Anderson-Hsiao estimator and

Table 3: Exploring the robustness 1

	AH	AB	B1	B2	GMM	Forest_dependent
L.Forest_rent	0.6917*** (0.0217)	0.6726*** (0.0217)	0.7235*** (0.0211)	0.7232*** (0.0209)	0.7740*** (0.0356)	0.6724*** (0.0314)
Elect	-0.4613*** (0.1712)	-0.4550*** (0.1666)	-0.4820*** (0.1706)	-0.4816*** (0.1706)	-0.4443** (0.1755)	-1.0796*** (0.3634)
Elect_Con	0.9793* (0.5024)	0.9559* (0.4897)	1.0333** (0.5002)	1.0322** (0.5002)	0.9780** (0.4880)	2.6876* (1.4295)
Polcon	-1.1156*** (0.2640)	-0.9707*** (0.2544)	-1.1063*** (0.2635)	-1.1053*** (0.2634)	-0.8760*** (0.2352)	-2.9584*** (0.8870)
Corruption	-0.1415*** (0.0545)	-0.1295** (0.0528)	-0.1558*** (0.0560)	-0.1556*** (0.0559)	-0.1313*** (0.0502)	-0.4696*** (0.1514)
GDPperCap	0.0000 (0.0000)	-0.0000 (0.0000)	0.0000 (0.0000)	0.0000 (0.0000)	0.0000 (0.0000)	-0.0005** (0.0002)
Depl	0.0497*** (0.0109)	0.0574*** (0.0105)	0.0571*** (0.0109)	0.0571*** (0.0109)	0.0551*** (0.0092)	0.1202*** (0.0223)
UrbanPop	0.0173 (0.0171)	0.0056 (0.0160)	0.0144 (0.0177)	0.0143 (0.0177)	0.0098 (0.0127)	0.0111 (0.0451)
Democ	-0.0008 (0.0045)	-0.0013 (0.0045)	-0.0011 (0.0044)	-0.0011 (0.0044)	-0.0020 (0.0043)	-0.0241 (0.0636)
<i>N</i>	2010	2010	2010	2010	2010	620
Country FE	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Year FE	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Countries	83	83	83	83	83	25

Notes: N=2010, t statistics in parentheses

* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

the Arellano-Bond estimator. The results are presented in the first two columns of table 3. We see that these two results support our findings. And above all, the coefficients are qualitatively and substantially similar: Competitive elections lead to cycles in forest rents.

We also test the robustness of our results by using different levels of bias to estimate our results. As specified above, Nickell's bias can be corrected according to three possible estimates of this bias. The one we used in our main model is the most restrictive possible. Columns 3 and 4 of table 3 present the results for the other two bias estimates. And here again, our results are confirmed, and the coefficients are substantially equal to those found in our main results.

6.2 Use of GMM method.

Among the possible methods, we could choose to estimate our dynamic panel model is the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM). However, we had chosen the generalized least squares corrected for Nickell's bias. In this part, we propose to re-estimate our primary model using GMM. This method is commonly used to estimate dynamic models because it solves a problem, that of endogeneity. Indeed, the presence of the lagged explained variable creates an endogeneity problem. And again, our results, presented in the fifth column of table 3, are robust to this alternative method. Furthermore, as in the other robustness tests, the coefficient is substantially equal to that of the main results.

6.3 Countries dependent on forest rents.

Our study takes into account developing countries without taking into account their level of dependence on forest resources. In this section, we intend to test the validity of our results by only retaining our sample countries that are highly dependent on forest resources. We constructed a sub-sample of countries with forest rents above the average. The results, presented in the sixth column of table 3, show once again that

our obtained results are robust and, even more, they are qualitatively similar.

6.4 Use of The use of additional control variables.

The penultimate test of robustness that we use is adding new control variables to show that our specification is stable and robust. What we are doing here is introducing several control variables likely to impact the level of forest rents, particularly during an election period. The first variable we introduce is the level of internal conflict within each country. This additional variable makes it possible to consider general instability and political instability in particular. This instability can impact the quality of the elections that must be held. The second variable that we incorporate for robustness is the level of socioeconomic conditions of the population. We get this variable from the ICRG database. The socioeconomic conditions of a population can make it remarkably docile to manipulation during an election period. Our results are presented in the three first column of table 4 and are still robust to these robustness tests.

6.5 Placebo tests

In this section, we perform placebo tests. For this, we have made shifts in the election dates to demonstrate that the cycles detected above do not appear during non-election periods. Indeed, the appearance of electoral cycles can be attributed to other cycles, such as cycles of corruption that appear during the same period. Therefore, we must ensure that the cycles captured are electoral cycles that only appear during the electoral period. In our exercise, we tried to detect cycles in the years following the elections. We have placed as election years the one, two, and three years after the elections. Results are presented in the four last columns of table 4. And in line with our expectations, we do not find cycles in forest rents during non-electoral periods. This result confirms our findings and constitutes the last series of robustness tests we implement.

Table 4: Exploring the robustness 2

	Conflict	Social	Exrate	Before	One year	Two year	Three years
L.Forest_rent	0.7274*** (0.0210)	0.7263*** (0.0211)	0.7278*** (0.0194)	0.7272*** (0.0208)	0.7267*** (0.0210)	0.7264*** (0.0209)	0.7275*** (0.0209)
Elect	-0.4954*** (0.1695)	-0.4817*** (0.1703)	-0.4854** (0.1973)				
Elect_Con	1.0620** (0.4981)	1.0285** (0.4993)	0.9868* (0.5682)				
Polcon	-1.0737*** (0.2642)	-1.1201*** (0.2629)	-1.0865*** (0.2809)	-0.9853*** (0.2647)	-1.0271*** (0.2651)	-1.0504*** (0.2529)	-0.9234*** (0.2630)
Corruption	-0.1473** (0.0574)	-0.1555*** (0.0559)	-0.1593*** (0.0582)	-0.1558*** (0.0562)	-0.1557*** (0.0561)	-0.1568*** (0.0562)	-0.1557*** (0.0559)
GDPperCap	0.0000 (0.0000)						
Depl	0.0572*** (0.0109)	0.0567*** (0.0109)	0.0561*** (0.0105)	0.0571*** (0.0108)	0.0572*** (0.0109)	0.0573*** (0.0107)	0.0568*** (0.0109)
UrbanPop	0.0145 (0.0177)	0.0154 (0.0179)	0.0165 (0.0179)	0.0150 (0.0178)	0.0153 (0.0177)	0.0153 (0.0177)	0.0151 (0.0178)
Democ	-0.0020 (0.0045)	-0.0009 (0.0044)	0.0010 (0.0046)	-0.0002 (0.0044)	-0.0003 (0.0044)	-0.0001 (0.0044)	-0.0003 (0.0044)
InternalConflict	-0.0432* (0.0244)						
SocioeconomicConditions		-0.0248 (0.0436)					
Exrate			0.0000** (0.0000)				
Before_elect				0.0003 (0.2040)			
Before_Con				0.1411 (0.5921)			
Elect1					-0.1540 (0.2028)		
Elect_Con1					0.4272 (0.5901)		
Elect2						-0.1092 (0.1975)	
Elect_Con2						0.5088 (0.5208)	
Elect3							0.1017 (0.1641)
Elect_Con3							-0.2293 (0.4981)
N	2010	2010	1971	2010	2010	2010	2010
Country FE	YES						
Year FE	YES						
Countries	83	83	83	83	83	83	83

Notes: N=2010, t statistics in parentheses

* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

7 Heterogeneity analysis

As mentioned above, our results are supposed to have a high degree of heterogeneity. We propose to test this, and the results are presented in Table 5. Firstly, we'll look at how results vary according to whether or not the elections are early, and then whether the candidate in power is represented in the elections. In addition, factors such as the level of corruption and individual freedoms may influence our results. We therefore also analyze the sensitivity of our results to these two factors.

7.1 The difference between staggered elections and regular elections

According to the literature (Uberti *et al.* (2019)), early elections do not allow the candidate in power to manipulate public opinion since the deadline would be too short. This is what we propose to test in this part. Our database allows us to divide the elections in two, depending on whether the elections are staggered or not. We, therefore, propose to test this by using our primary model on staggered elections. The result is presented in the first column of the table 5. We see in this case that staggered competitive elections do not give rise to the manipulation of forest rent. However, generally displaced elections result in higher forest rents. This is what we see in our results through the positive and significant coefficient of the variable *Delayed* in the first column. This result is explained by the fact that the delayed elections in our base can be elections that have been brought forward or postponed. If the elections have been postponed, the incumbent president has time to manipulate.

7.2 In case of representation of the candidate in power

We wanted to test the heterogeneity of our results by verifying whether cycles did indeed occur when candidates for power were represented. When the candidate stands for re-election or if his political party stands for re-election, he has every reason to

Table 5: Exploring the heterogeneity

	Delayed	Incub_run	Dont_run	Hight_currup	Low_currup	Hight_Freed	Low_Freed
L.Forest_rent	0.7285*** (0.0208)	0.7293*** (0.0209)	0.7272*** (0.0210)	0.7998*** (0.0252)	0.6778*** (0.0254)	0.8235*** (0.0243)	0.7140*** (0.0239)
Delayed	0.6080* (0.3227)						
Delayed_comp	-0.8011 (1.0370)						
Polcon	-0.9374*** (0.2551)	-1.0434*** (0.2597)	-0.9995*** (0.2570)	-0.3835* (0.2279)	-1.6981*** (0.4465)	-0.3984* (0.2063)	-1.5872*** (0.4616)
Corruption	-0.1537*** (0.0559)	-0.1504*** (0.0557)	-0.1565*** (0.0558)	-0.0236 (0.0452)	-0.3225*** (0.1107)	-0.0816** (0.0389)	-0.2329*** (0.0898)
GDPperCap	0.0000 (0.0000)	0.0000 (0.0000)	0.0000 (0.0000)	-0.0000 (0.0000)	-0.0000 (0.0001)	0.0000 (0.0000)	0.0000 (0.0001)
Depl	0.0570*** (0.0109)	0.0571*** (0.0109)	0.0571*** (0.0109)	0.0632*** (0.0150)	0.0602*** (0.0145)	0.0028 (0.0142)	0.0702*** (0.0128)
UrbanPop	0.0141 (0.0178)	0.0138 (0.0177)	0.0151 (0.0177)	-0.0077 (0.0140)	0.0476 (0.0307)	0.0108 (0.0103)	0.0131 (0.0287)
Democ	0.0002 (0.0045)	-0.0010 (0.0044)	-0.0007 (0.0045)	-0.0128* (0.0067)	0.0055 (0.0082)	-0.0054* (0.0031)	0.0133 (0.0097)
Incub_Run		-0.6604*** (0.1884)					
Incub_comp		1.1124** (0.5664)					
Dont_run			-0.1863 (0.2181)				
Dont_comp			0.6009 (0.5650)				
Elect				0.1494 (0.1822)	-1.0424*** (0.2943)	-0.2938* (0.1578)	-0.6089* (0.3245)
Elect_Con				-0.2965 (0.4645)	1.7423* (0.9128)	0.7660** (0.3729)	0.8926 (1.0300)
<i>N</i>	2010	2010	2010	1049	961	907	1103
Country FE	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Year FE	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Countries	83	83	83	41	42	37	46

Notes: N=2010, t statistics in parentheses

* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

carry out manipulations to signal his competence to be re-elected. Thus, one should see cycles in the case of the representation of the candidate in power. To test this, we break our elections down into two. Elections in which the president in power is running and elections in which the president in power is not running. The results are presented in the second and third columns of the table 5. Consistent with our expectations, election cycles appear when the ruling candidate runs for office again. This can be read in the last two columns of our heterogeneity table. We find results consistent with the literature.

7.3 Depending on the level of corruption

We also tested the sensitivity of our results by considering the level of corruption in the countries. While true that we take into account the level of competitiveness of the elections, the level of corruption within the country can affect political cycles. Corruption can reduce the need to increase rents since results can be manipulated, for example. To test this, we have divided our countries into two groups according to the median. We have taken our most complete specifications on these two different groups. Our results presented in the fourth and the fifth column of table 5 are not surprising. Political cycles at the level of forest rents are observed only at the level of countries with a low level of corruption, i.e., at the level of the group with the lowest level of corruption.

7.4 Depending on the level of freedom

According to the literature, the population's education level, the age of democracy, or even access to information are factors conditioning the probability of the appearance of political cycles. Indeed, these different factors affect the ability of the voting population to understand the manipulations of politicians and their intentions. We proposed to test the sensitivity of our results according to the level of freedom in the different countries. Our results presented in the two last columns of table 5 show that countries

with a high level of human freedoms experience political cycles in terms of political rents.

8 Conclusion

Initially, our objective was to detect the presence of possible electoral cycles at the level of natural resource rents in developing countries, these countries, with institutions still under construction and nascent democracies. We worked on a sample of eighty-three (83) countries. Moreover, we used the Nickel bias-corrected generalized least squares estimator proposed by Bruno (2005) and used by Gootjes *et al.* (2021); Debrun *et al.* (2008); Bogliacino *et al.* (2012), to highlight possible forest rent cycles. This estimator has the advantage of being operational even on small samples. Overall, our results suggest that resource rents in developing countries are not subject to cycles in the case of elections in general. However, the competitiveness of elections seems to be a factor that conditions electoral cycles in natural resource rents.

We tested the robustness of our results using the Anderson-Hsiao and Arellano-Bover estimators. We also re-estimated our primary model using less restrictive Nickel bias corrections. In a third robustness test, we used the GMM estimator and added additional control variables. In order to differentiate the cycles brought to light within forest rents from those of other resources, we looked for cycles at the level of other natural resources, excluding forest resources. Finally, we reduced our sample to countries dependent on forest resources. Our results come out robust after all these tests. The heterogeneity analysis showed us that it is mainly the elections during which the president is running for re-election. These cycles appear only in low corrupted countries and countries with high human freedom. However, our work suffers from some limitations that could be sources of extension of the present study. The first is using total natural resource rents in place of the rents received by the state. This is beyond our control and is due to the lack of data. The Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative (EITI)²

²<https://eiti.org/fr>

database³, which is the basis for this information, exists but is too recent. In the coming years, as the time horizon of the database lengthens, higher-quality work could be done. Another limitation of our work is that the different channels could have been tested more thoroughly, depending on data availability and completeness. These include, for example, the number of operating permits granted or the tax rate in the mining sector over our study period. Indeed, it would be interesting to study how operating permits evolve with elections. As we have seen, elements of the literature show us that in certain precise countries, these exploitation permits were subject to cycles.

These different results lead us to draw some conclusions. The few competitive elections that take place generate cycles because of the manipulation of candidates for power due to the youth of democracies. On this basis, economic policy recommendations can be made. Indeed, manipulation for re-election purposes has adverse effects on the economy. Therefore, having strong institutions, including independent structures for natural resource management, is crucial. Also, since a high level of democracy is associated with an absence of cycles, developing countries should be encouraged to continue their march toward democracy, which cannot be done without the help of the international community. However, these various measures that will be taken will be implemented by the same individuals who hold power. The most effective way to do this is to build a vibrant civil society. This refers to the human capital of countries. And therefore, a medium and long-term fight against these political manipulations of rents is also to invest in the education of the population so that they can understand the political game during the election period.

³<https://eiti.org/fr/donnees-ouvertes>

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Annexe

Table 6: List of countries included in the analysis

Albania	Algeria	Angola	Argentina	Armenia	Azerbaijan	Bangladesh	Belarus
Bolivia	Botswana	Brazil	Bulgaria	Burkina Faso	Cameroon	Chile	China
Colombia	Congo, Dem. Rep.	Costa Rica	Cote d'Ivoire	Ecuador	El Salvador	Ethiopia	Finland
Gabon	Gambia	Ghana	Guatemala	Guinea	Guinea-Bissau	Guyana	Haiti
Honduras	Hungary	India	Indonesia	Jamaica	Jordan	Kazakhstan	Kenya
Kuwait	Lebanon	Liberia	Libya	Madagascar	Malawi	Malaysia	Mali
Mexico	Moldova	Mongolia	Morocco	Mozambique	Namibia	Nicaragua	Niger
Nigeria	Pakistan	Panama	Papua New Guinea	Paraguay	Peru	Philippines	Poland
Qatar	Saudi Arabia	Senegal	Serbia	Sierra Leone	South Africa	Sri Lanka	Sudan
Tanzania	Thailand	Togo	Tunisia	Turkey	Uganda	Ukraine	Uruguay
Vietnam	Zambia	Zimbabwe					

Figure 4: Correlation

Table 8: List and sources of variables

Variable	Definitions	Sources
Forest rents	Annual forest rents of countries as a percentage of GDP	World Bank (2019) Et The Changing Wealth of Nations: Measuring Sustainable Development in the New Millennium (World Bank, 2011)

Political constraints	Political constraint index: the number of veto actors in the political system	POLCON by Witold Jerzy Henisz
Elect	Variable from the pre-election period	National Elections Across Democracy and Autocracy Dataset, 5.0 (NELDA)
Elect_Con	Elections taking into account their level of competitiveness	Calculation of authors using Elect and Polcon variables
Corruption	Level of corruption within a country	International Country Risk Guide ⁴
GDP per capita	GDP per capita in constant dollars	World Bank (2019)
Urbanization rate	Share of the urban population in the total population	World Bank (2019)
Level of democracy	Degree of democracy in the country	POLITY5 Political Regime Characteristics and Transitions, 1800-2018

⁴<https://www.prsgroup.com/explore-our-products/icrg/>

Exchange rate	Official annual exchange rate (Average for the period)	World Bank (2019)
Dependency ratio	Dependency ratio in the country as a percentage of the working-age population	World Bank (2019)

Table 7: Correlation Table

	Forest_rent	GDPperCap	Democ	UrbanPop	Corruption	Depl	Polcon	Elect	Elect_Con
Forest_rent	1.0***	-0.26***	-0.03	-0.48***	-0.13***	0.29***	-0.12***	0.01	-0.05*
GDPperCap	-0.26***	1.0***	0.03	0.59***	0.28***	0.07**	0.04*	-0.06**	-0.0
Democ	-0.03	0.03	1.0***	0.0	0.17***	-0.07**	0.36***	-0.01	0.09***
UrbanPop	-0.48***	0.59***	0.0	1.0***	0.19***	-0.05*	0.06**	-0.01	0.06**
Corruption	-0.13***	0.28***	0.17***	0.19***	1.0***	-0.22***	0.14***	0.01	0.05*
Depl	0.29***	0.07**	-0.07**	-0.05*	-0.22***	1.0***	-0.18***	-0.03	-0.06**
Polcon	-0.12***	0.04*	0.36***	0.06**	0.14***	-0.18***	1.0***	0.0	0.27***
Elect	0.01	-0.06**	-0.01	-0.01	0.01	-0.03	0.0	1.0***	0.76***
Elect_Con	-0.05*	-0.0	0.09***	0.06**	0.05*	-0.06**	0.27***	0.76***	1.0***

Figure 5: Relationship between Forest rents and tenure